

Mainstreaming AI in the training cycle: insights from designing capacity development learning experiences

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Abstract. This half-day workshop aims to share experiences and insights on integrating AI throughout the entire training cycle - from analysis to design, development, implementation, and evaluation. Grounded in global, human-centered frameworks for AI in education, such as the UNESCO AI competency frameworks for teachers and students, this interactive, hands-on session will address the critical question of how AI can enhance high-quality learning experiences for capacity development. The workshop will explore the benefits and challenges of mainstreaming AI in learning experiences, showcasing use cases and prototypes from learning design practices at IIEP-UNESCO, WHO Academy, ITC and UNSSC with practical relevance for professionals working across the training cycle.

Keywords: AI Use Cases, AI for Capacity Development.

1 Proposed agenda of the workshop (4 hours)

1.1 Welcome and introduction to the workshop (15 minutes) (speakers: Anne-Elisabeth Akrasi, Jimena Pereyra)

Presentation of the human-centred approach to AI in education, as defined by UNESCO

Overview of the whole training cycle and the role of AI in each phase to enhance teaching and learning practices

1.2 Integrating AI in course design and development: insights emerging from IIEP-UNESCO's practice (45 minutes) (speakers: Anne-Elisabeth Akrasi, Jimena Pereyra)

Short presentation: The IIEP Teaching and Learning guide and its global learner-centered pedagogical model

Demonstration: IIEP AI-layered learning design card deck and prompts as tools for learning design

Hands-on activity: Participants will be given step-by-step guidance and invited to use the IIEP learning design card deck and prompts to prototype a short training module on AI

1.3 Break (30 minutes)

1.4 Leveraging AI for engaging, personalized learning: insights emerging from WHO Academy's practice (45 minutes) (speaker: Ioanna Kosteridou)

Short presentation: The WHO Learning Academy and its AI-powered learning platform to deliver competency-based learning at scale

Demonstration: AI applications for adaptive and personalized learning experiences

Hands-on activity: Co-creating AI-powered prototypes to design and implement personalized learning paths

1.5 Leveraging AI for teaching and grading in e-learning: insights from a recent pilot and ITC SME Trade Academy innovation (45 minutes) (speaker: Shaun Lake)

Presentation: Exploring how the SME Trade Academy has successfully integrated AI to enhance learning outcomes and improve the effectiveness of e-learning at scale

Demonstration: Showcasing AI's role as a virtual teacher and grader, helping learners gain a deeper understanding of complex concepts

Interactive activity: Crafting effective prompts for AI-generated e-learning assessments

1.6 Leveraging AI for supporting self-directed learning: insights from UNSSC's Blue Line Platform (45 minutes) (speaker: Sofia Exarchou)

Presentation: UNSSC Blue Line and use of AI to support self-directed learning. What worked, lessons learned, and mistakes made along the way.

Demonstration: AI application for self-directed learning in the Blue Line.

Hands-on activity: Co-designing the building blocks of AI for self-directed learning.

1.7 Wrap-up (15 minutes)

2 Logistical information

Anticipated number of participants:20-30

Technical equipment: Device with Internet access

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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